

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DESTINATION IMAGE, SATISFACTION AND REVISIT INTENTION: AN EMPIRICAL VIETNAMESE TOURIST VISITS DA LAT CITY

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Abstract

This study aims to measure the mutual impact relationship between destination image, satisfaction, and intention to revisit Da Lat by domestic Vietnamese tourists. Quantitative research methods were used and collected 200 Vietnamese tourists. After filtering, 176 value answers were used for analysis. The research used SPSS 22.0 to measure reliability, satisfaction, and correlation between destination image, satisfaction, and intention to revisit. The findings showed that destination image (environment, infrastructure, and entertainment) positively influence Vietnamese revisit intention. In addition, destination image (security and safety, environment, infrastructure, and entertainment activities) positively influences Vietnamese satisfaction. Furthermore, overall satisfaction positively influences Vietnamese revisit intention. The study provides a deeper understanding of the destination image and satisfaction in sharpening tourist revisit intention. These findings provide additional information for developing the destination image, reinforcing the satisfaction of domestic tourists to increase their intention to revisit Da Lat.

Keywords: Destination Image; Satisfaction; Revisit Intention; Vietnamese Tourist; Da Lat City

Introduction

After the COVID-19 pandemic, various economic sectors have implemented strong strategies and advancements to revive the country's economy (Chi & Phuong, 2022; Roach et al., 2021). The tourism industry has been prioritized as a pioneer in revival and development. Many localities have launched campaign programs to attract visitors, resulting in a 168.3% increase in domestic tourism in 2022 compared to the plan and surpassing pre-pandemic levels (Vietnamnews, 2022). This rise in domestic tourism can be attributed to limited long-distance travel, high costs, and uncertainty regarding pandemic safety (Vietnamnews, 2022). Da Lat City is one of the "hot trends" and perennially popular destinations. Da Lat has always been a favorite destination for domestic tourism in Vietnam. The total number of overnight visitors to Da Lat in the first six months of 2022 reached over 3.1 million, a 90.3% increase over the same period in 2021 (Mai, 2022). Da Lat has always been a favorite destination for domestic tourism in Vietnam. Thus, the study was conducted to understand Da Lat's destination image and find solutions to improve visitor satisfaction and increase intentions to return to Da Lat by Vietnamese tourists.

Previous studies investigated the influence of destination image factors (including seven elements) on destination image perception (Králiková et al., 2020; D.-B. Park & Nunkoo, 2013). The model also identified that destination image overall positively affects tourist loyalty (Králiková et al., 2020). Loyalty in the model is understood as the intention to return or recommend to others. The study on the factors affecting the intention to return of domestic tourists: The case of tourism destinations in An Giang province reexamined the impact of factors such as destination image, tourist experience, and travel barriers on the intention to return of domestic tourists to tourism destinations in An Giang province (Phuc & Dung, 2022). The research results showed that destination image and tourist experience positively impact the intention to return. In contrast, travel barriers have a negative effect on the intention to

return (Phuc & Dung, 2022). In addition, customer satisfaction is also influenced by many factors, such as product quality, service quality, price, situational factors, and individual factors (Sato et al., 2018). Furthermore, the relationship between destination image, satisfaction, and revisit intention has been established in previous studies (Abdullah & Lui, 2018; Allameh et al., 2015; Park et al., 2019; Rasoolimanesh et al., 2021). However, the studies focus on destinations like Da Lat, which is still rare in the literature.

Thus, the study aims to understand the relationship between destination image, satisfaction, and revisit intention in Da Lat tourism. Furthermore, the study focuses on domestic tourists who have visited Da Lat and its tourist destinations and beauty from the perspective of domestic visitors as the subject. The study seeks to evaluate the experiences of domestic tourists when visiting Da Lat and identify the factors that contribute to their satisfaction and dissatisfaction during their vacation and travel in Da Lat. The study used the SPSS 22.0 software to analyze the data through surveys to achieve the research purposes. The outcome of this study will contribute to the development of tourism in the country in general and Da Lat tourism in particular. Moreover, the analysis can serve as marketing material for tourism and destination marketing organizations.

Literature Review

2.1. Da Lat City

Da Lat - a city on the Lam Vien plateau with a diverse range of unique flowers and a very characteristic climate. Visitors will feel the gentle and cool air year-round when coming to Da Lat. Surrounding us are majestic mountains, vast forests, and abundant plant life. When visiting Da Lat, tourists come to an area with endless flower fields, friendly locals, unique cultural identities of the local people, famous landscapes, and ideal tourist destinations. It would be remiss not to mention the cuisine of Da Lat. Da Lat's culinary culture combines the culinary quintessence of many different regions. The most notable among them are the three dishes recognized by the Vietnam Culinary Culture Association (VCCA) as being in the "Top 100 delicious dishes of Vietnam": pork leg stew with artichoke, Da Lat flower hotpot, and Da Lat vegetables with vinegar and chrysanthemum sauce (Baolamdong, 2022).

Historically, Da Lat has been likened to the "miniature melting pot" of Vietnam, with people from all over coming here. Alongside this, unique cultural traits from every region have created a fusion of cultures from the East to the West, from the North to the South. The French contributed to the enlightenment of this region with grand architecture influenced by European architecture. Some notable works include Da Lat Teachers' College, Da Lat Train Station, and The Church of the Chicken. Later, Da Lat knew how to exploit and transform its natural treasures to promote tourism and development. Infrastructure was developed with nature, such as the Lam Vien Square, Xuan Huong Lake, and Da Lat Strawberry Gardens. These are destinations that attract a large number of tourists. Eco-tourism areas and cafes also appeared. They were built to embellish the beautiful and magnificent nature of Da Lat, such as the Hoa Son Dien Trang eco-tourism area, the Da Tien eco-tourism area, the Lung Chung Cafe, and Hunter Café.

2.2. Destination Image

Destination image is visible in the classic definition: "A tourism destination is a geographical unit visited by tourists being a self-contained center" (Burkart & Medlik, 1974, p. 46). Destination image expresses all objective knowledge, prejudices, imagination, and emotional thoughts of an individual or group about a particular location (Lawson & Baud-Bovy, 1977).

Meanwhile, Mill and Morrison (1992) argued that a tourist destination is a place where interdependent factors must be combined to create a satisfying vacation experience for tourists. These factors include attractions, facilities, infrastructure, transportation, and accommodations (Mill & Morrison, 1992).

The Theory of Planning Behaviour (TPB) suggests that someone with a positive attitude toward a particular destination is more likely to choose that destination for their vacation (Ajzen, 1991). Tourist behavior can be divided into three stages: before, during, and after the trip. Specifically, tourist behavior includes decision-making, website experiences, evaluation of the travel experience, and post-travel behavior (Williams, 2003). The study characteristics and intentions of cruise passengers to return to the Caribbean for land-based vacation showed the attributes of cruise passengers and their booking methods for their cruise vacation and identified factors that influence their intention to return for a land-based vacation (Baker & Unni, 2019). Furthermore, previous studies show the impact of destination images on tourist behavior (Abdullah & Lui, 2018; Kim, 2018; Som & Badarneh, 2011; Tosun et al., 2015). Therefore, based on previous research, it is evident that the destination image significantly influences the intention of tourists to return (Bigné Alcañiz et al., 2009; Kim, 2018). Thus, the image of a tourist destination is an essential factor that affects the intention of tourists to revisit, and destinations with widely known images are more attractive to tourists (Kim, 2018; Tosun et al., 2015). Based on the above evidence, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): The destination image of Da Lat positively impacts the intention of domestic tourists in Vietnam to revisit.

2.3. Satisfaction

Tourists have their expectations before arriving at their chosen destination, which can include images of the location, pricing, or the quality of services or products based on recommendations from friends and family or information and pictures found online (Güzel et al., 2020; Nguyen, 2020; Sato et al., 2018). Once the tourists arrive and experience the quality of their chosen destination, they can compare it to their previous expectations to determine if their trip was satisfactory (Nguyen, 2020; Quintal & Polczynski, 2010). If tourists' experiences exceed their expectations, they are delighted with their journey (Jiang et al., 2020). Conversely, if their experience at the destination is uncomfortable, they will not be satisfied (Jiang et al., 2020; Sato et al., 2018). Researchers of destination images have noticed that destinations with more positive photos are more likely to be preferred by tourists when making decisions (Abdullah & Lui, 2018; Nguyen, 2020; Sharma & Nayak, 2019). Furthermore, the experienced image of a destination positively influences the perception and satisfaction of tourists. A more favorable impression leads to higher levels of satisfaction among tourists (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003).

Previous studies in Vietnamese tourism identified the relationship between destination image and satisfaction (Thao et al., 2020; Vang et al., 2021; Vu & Vang, 2020). The factors that affect the satisfaction of domestic tourists were studied in Ho Chi Minh City (Thao et al., 2020). The study collected data from 530 domestic tourists and applied an exploratory factor analysis model. The results showed that the factors that influence the satisfaction of tourists are as follows: destination brand image, diverse and hospitable services, accommodation, food and beverage, transportation and cleanliness, support services, events, and safety. The study revealed that these factors directly and positively impact the satisfaction of domestic tourists in Ho Chi Minh City, with the destination brand image having the most decisive influence (Thao et al., 2020). Furthermore, the survey was collected from tourists who had visited My Tho City (Vu & Vang, 2020). The research proposed a model consisting of seven factors influencing tourists' satisfaction while visiting My Tho. The research results revealed that the satisfaction

of tourists is directly and positively influenced by the seven factors of the destination image, which are natural features, product price, infrastructure, tour guidance, tourism resources, emotional value, reliability, and service capacity, ranking in descending order of impact (Vu & Vang, 2020). The effect of destination image on domestic tourists' satisfaction with Dong Thap tourism destination in Vietnam (Vang et al., 2021). The research findings indicate that the perceived image is the starting point for forming the emotional image. Both emotional and perception images directly and positively impact the overall picture. Still, only components of perception image and overall image have a direct impact on tourist satisfaction. Additionally, the study finds an indirect relationship between perception image and overall image through emotional image, an indirect relationship between perception image and satisfaction through overall image, the progression from emotional image to the overall image, and an indirect relationship between emotional image and satisfaction through overall image (Vang et al., 2021). Thus, the study proposes the hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2 (H2): The destination image (Da Lat) positively influences the satisfaction of domestic tourists in Vietnam.

2.4. Revisit Intention

The intention to return of a tourist is the desire of travelers to visit a destination they have been to before (Kim, 2018; Park et al., 2019; Som & Badarneh, 2011). The intention to return is influenced by many factors, such as the image of the destination, quality of experience, perceived value, and satisfaction (Park et al., 2019; Rasoolimanesh et al., 2021; Seetanah et al., 2018; Tosun et al., 2015). In addition, many tourists want to return to a destination if they enjoyed it during their first visit (Akgün et al., 2020; Papadimitriou et al., 2015). Moreover, loyalty to a particular destination is reflected in the intention to return and willingness to recommend it to others (Chen & Tsai, 2007; Oppermann, 2000). The study on satisfaction and desire to return among domestic tourists in Soc Trang province (Trang & Loan, 2012). The study used a Likert 5 scale and proposed an Importance Performance Analysis model and level of satisfaction for tourism companies in Soc Trang. The results showed that tourist satisfaction was directly proportional to their intention to return. However, there were also cases of tourists who were inclined to explore and did not want to repeat their travel behavior, which could explain why they had no intention of returning to the same destination despite their high satisfaction. On the other hand, destination brand equity and authenticity positively and directly affect tourists' revisit intention and indirectly influence tourists' revisit intention by mediating tourist satisfaction (Shi et al., 2022). Based on the evidence presented, the study proposes the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Tourist satisfaction positively impacts the intention to return among domestic tourists when visiting Da Lat.

Figure 1. Research framework

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Measurement

The study used a questionnaire to collect information about Da Lat's destination image through the lens of Vietnamese domestic tourists, their satisfaction, and their intention to return. The questions were constructed based on the hypotheses and theoretical foundations adapted from the literature. The survey included a total of 32 questions divided into four main sections. A Likert 5 scale was used for all inquiries. Section 1 included 17 questions about the destination image of Da Lat, which was adapted and modified from previous studies (Beerli & Martín, 2004; Ha Nam Khanh, 2022); section 2 included five questions about tourist satisfaction adapted from earlier studies (Del Bosque & San Martín, 2008; Gök & Sayın, 2015); section 3 had four questions about the intention to return to Da Lat, adapted from previous studies (Gök & Sayın, 2015; Latiff & Ng, 2015); and the final section included five questions about demography.

3.2. Data Collection And Analysis

The research first conducted a pilot survey with ten students from the Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology and Education and three experts in the tourism industry to verify the value, accuracy, and necessity of the questions. After the pilot survey, the questionnaire was distributed through a web page for domestic tourists in Vietnam from March 14, 2023, to March 25, 2023. The study used a convenient sample method. The questionnaire was updated on Google Forms, then a link and QR code were created. After that, the link was notified to domestic tourists via Gmail, Facebook, Instagram, and Zalo.

Additionally, the randomly scanned QR codes of people on the street diversify the survey samples and increase the accuracy of the research. Then, the study collected information from respondents and excluded those who answered: "Never been to Da Lat." The study conducted 200 samples of domestic tourists; after removing participants who had not traveled to Da Lat, 176 representatives were valid for analysis.

The study used SPSS 22.0 statistical method to describe the characteristics of the study participants; describe the observed variables of each factor; test the reliability of each construct; and analyze the correlations between destination image, satisfaction, and revisit intention.

4. Data Analysis

4.1. Demographics

SPSS is used to analyze data collected through survey research. The following is a descriptive statistic on gender, age, marital status, education, and occupation of valid survey samples (n=176). The percentage of the male was 42%, while the female was 58%. Most of the participants were between the ages of 18 and 29 (87.5%). A large percentage (85.8%) was single. Regarding education, 69.3% of the participants had a bachelor's degree.

Table 1. Demographic

Items		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	74	42
	Female	102	58
Age	Under 18	2	1.1
	18 - 29	154	87.5
	30 - 40	13	7.4
	41 - 50	7	4.0
Married status	Single	151	85.8
	Married	25	14.2
Education	High school	22	12.5
	Bachelor	122	69.3
	Graduated	32	18.2
Occupation	Officer	14	8.0
	Private company	15	8.5
	Student	113	64.2
	Own business	15	8.5
	Others	19	10.8

4.2. Constructs Analysis

4.2.1. Destination Image

Looking at the data collected, variables related to environmental observation and entertainment activities are rated quite highly by tourists, unlike human factors, which are relatively low (Table 2). The three attributes that tourists rated the highest are “This picturesque destination boasts a plethora of beautiful and charming landscapes, from quaint villages to breathtaking jungles” (M=4.51, SD=.881), “It is a popular tourist hotspot that attracts visitors.” (M=4.49, SD=.448), and “Da Lat is renowned for its cool and refreshing climate, which provides a welcome escape from the sweltering heat of other regions in Vietnam.” (M=4.42, SD=.910). The three attributes with the lowest ratings are “There are clear efforts being made to adhere to food safety regulations.” (M=3.72, SD=.848), “The environment in Da Lat is largely untouched and pristine, making it a refreshing change from polluted cities.” (M=3.79, SD=.978), and “The food and beverage facilities are maintained at a high level of cleanliness, ensuring a comfortable and hygienic dining experience.” (M=3.81, SD=.831).

4.2.2. Satisfaction Analysis

Table 3 shows the high satisfaction levels of tourists with the environment scenery (M=4.22, SD=.881) and activities in Da Lat (M=4.18, SD=.826). However, tourists are moderately

satisfied with the variables related to security and safety in Da Lat (M=3.95, SD=.834) and the human factor (M=3.98, SD=.878).

4.2.3. Revisit Intention Analysis

The result indicated that the intention of domestic tourists to return is quite high. However, it should be noted that the attribute with the highest level of research involvement is “I am eager to plan another trip to Da Lat, this time with my loved ones, and create more happy memories together.” (M=4.36 SD=.883) and the attribute with the lowest evaluation is “I have set a goal to revisit Da Lat within the next six months, as I believe there are always new things to discover and enjoy in this charming city.” (M=3.82, SD=1.075) (Table 4).

4.3. Cronbach’s Alpha Analysis

Cronbach's alpha analysis was used to check the reliability of each construct. The scale is accepted when Cronbach's alpha score is greater than or equal to 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019). Therefore, table 5.5 shows that Cronbach's alpha of destination image (Cronbach's alpha = 0.95), satisfaction (Cronbach's alpha = 0.886), and intention to return (Cronbach's alpha = 0.85) all exceed 0.7. Thus, all items were well established with reliability levels within the acceptable range (Table 5).

Table 2. Destination Image Analysis

Destination image	Mean	SD
Security and safety		
In Da Lat, the maintenance of law and order is satisfactory.	3.39	.842
There are clear efforts being made to adhere to food safety regulations.	3.72	.848
The city is ensuring the safety of its residents and visitors by enforcing traffic regulations.	3.90	.920
Environment		
Da Lat is renowned for its cool and refreshing climate, which provides a welcome escape from the sweltering heat of other regions in Vietnam.	4.42	.910
This picturesque destination boasts a plethora of beautiful and charming landscapes, from quaint villages to breathtaking jungles.	4.51	.881
It is a popular tourist hotspot that attracts visitors.	4.49	.848
The environment in Da Lat is largely untouched and pristine, making it a refreshing change from polluted cities.	3.79	.978
Human factor		
Local people in Da Lat exhibit warm hospitality and friendliness.	3.39	.932
Service staff in Da Lat demonstrate a high level of enthusiasm.	3.85	.876
Service staff in Da Lat demonstrate a high level of professionalism.	3.86	.880
Infrastructure		
Numerous modern and safe transportation options provide convenient access to all areas of Da Lat.	3.87	.814
The food and beverage facilities are maintained at a high level of cleanliness, ensuring a comfortable and hygienic dining experience.	3.81	.831
The accommodations, including homestays, guesthouses, and hotels, are also well-maintained and provide visitors with a safe and comfortable stay.	3.99	.838
Da Lat boasts a diverse and rich culinary culture, offering various delicious and unique dining options.	4.10	.895
Entertainment activities		
Da Lat offers numerous entertainment options, from thrilling activities to laid-back attractions.	4.04	1.016

Visitors can also browse the various souvenirs and locally sourced products in town.	4.26	.868
The region offers plenty of serene and tranquil sights to enjoy, making it a perfect destination for those seeking relaxation.	4.41	.788

Note: SD: Standard deviation

Table 3. Satisfaction Analysis

Satisfaction	Mean	SD
Security and safety	3.95	.834
Environment	4.22	.881
Human factor	3.98	.878
Infrastructure	4.01	.898
Entertainment activities	4.18	.826

Note: SD: Standard deviation

Table 4. Revisit Intention Analysis

Revisit intention	Mean	SD
I am committed to sharing positive experiences and impressions of Da Lat with others.	4.16	.801
I look forward to recommending Da Lat to my friends, colleagues, and anyone who is interested in visiting a beautiful and unique destination in Vietnam.	4.23	.912
I am eager to plan another trip to Da Lat, this time with my loved ones, and create more happy memories together.	4.36	.883
I have set a goal to revisit Da Lat within the next six months, as I believe there are always new things to discover and enjoy in this charming city	3.82	1.075

Note: SD: Standard deviation

Table 5. Cronbach's Alpha Analysis

Construct/Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Destination image	.949
In Da Lat, the maintenance of law and order is satisfactory.	.947
There are clear efforts being made to adhere to food safety regulations.	.947
The city is ensuring the safety of its residents and visitors by enforcing traffic regulations.	.948
Da Lat is renowned for its cool and refreshing climate, which provides a welcome escape from the sweltering heat of other regions in Vietnam.	.947
This picturesque destination boasts a plethora of beautiful and charming landscapes, from quaint villages to breathtaking jungles.	.946
It is a popular tourist hotspot that attracts visitors.	.946
The environment in Da Lat is mainly untouched and pristine, making it a refreshing change from polluted cities.	.946
Local people in Da Lat exhibit warm hospitality and friendliness.	.946
Service staff in Da Lat demonstrate a high level of enthusiasm.	.945
Service staff in Da Lat demonstrate a high level of professionalism.	.944
Numerous modern and safe transportation options provide convenient access to all areas of Da Lat.	.945
The food and beverage facilities are maintained at a high level of cleanliness, ensuring a comfortable and hygienic dining experience.	.945
The accommodations, including homestays, guesthouses, and hotels, are also well-maintained and provide visitors with a safe and comfortable stay.	.945
Da Lat boasts a diverse and rich culinary culture, offering various delicious and unique dining options.	.946
Da Lat offers numerous entertainment options, from thrilling activities to laid-back attractions.	.948
Visitors can also browse the various souvenirs and locally sourced products in town.	.947
The region offers plenty of serene and tranquil sights to enjoy, making it a perfect destination for those seeking relaxation.	.948
Satisfaction	.886
Security and safety	.869
Environment	.870
Human factor	.853
Infrastructure	.848
Entertainment activities	.863
Revisit intention	.853
I am committed to sharing positive experiences and impressions of Da Lat with others.	.817
I look forward to recommending Da Lat to my friends, colleagues, and anyone who is interested in visiting a beautiful and unique destination in Vietnam.	.772
I am eager to plan another trip to Da Lat, this time with my loved ones, and create more happy memories together.	.784
I have set a goal to revisit Da Lat within the next six months, as I believe there are always new things to discover and enjoy in this charming city	.776

4.4. Correlation Analysis

4.4.1. Destination Image And Revisit Intention

The results of analyzing the correlation between images of Da Lat's tourist destination factors and the intention of domestic tourists to revisit intention (hypothesis 1) are presented in Table 6 and Table 7. The factors "Environmental" ($\beta = 0.41$, P-value = $0.000 < 0.05$), "Infrastructure" ($\beta = 0.211$, P-value = $0.043 < 0.05$), and "Entertainment activities" ($\beta = 0.205$, P-value = $0.008 < 0.05$) of images of Da Lat's tourist destinations all have an impact on the intention of tourists to return. Furthermore, the factors "Safety and security" and "Human" do not have statistically significant meanings for the intention of visitors to return to Da Lat because their significance level (Sig.) is 0.299 and 0.859, respectively, which is greater than 0.05, so the hypothesis that these two factors directly affect visitors' intention to return to Da Lat is rejected.

Table 6. Summary of multiple regression analysis for destination image and revisit intention.

Source	<i>SS</i>	<i>DF</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Model	64.36	5	12.872	55.994*
Error	39.08	170	.230	
Total	103.44	175		

Note: Dependent variable: revisit intention, * $p < .001$

Table 7. The multiple regression analysis results between destination image and revisits intention.

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Constant</i>	.338	.238		1.422	.157
Security and safety	.079	.076	.077	1.041	.299
Environment	.416	.078	.411	5.308	.000**
Human factor	-.014	.081	-.015	-.177	.859
Infrastructure	.225	.111	.211	2.036	.043**
Entertainment activities	.206	.077	.205	2.674	.008**

R = .789, $R^2 = .622$, Adj $R^2 = .611$

Note: Dependent variable: revisit intention, ** $p < .05$

4.4.2. Destination Image And Satisfaction

The images of Da Lat as a tourist destination significantly impact domestic tourists' satisfaction (hypothesis 2) (Table 8 and Table 9). The results of the correlation analysis show that four factors of Da Lat's image affect tourist satisfaction: security and safety ($\beta = 0.232$, P-value = 0.000), environmental scenery ($\beta = 0.172$, P-value = 0.007), infrastructure ($\beta = 0.260$, P-value = 0.003), and entertainment activities ($\beta = 0.233$, P-value = 0.000). Moreover, these four factors explain 74.7% of the variation in domestic tourists' satisfaction while visiting Da Lat ($R^2 = 0.747$).

Table 8. Summary of multiple regression analysis for destination image and satisfaction

Source	<i>SS</i>	<i>DF</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Model	66.900	5	13.380	100.339*
Error	22.669	170	.133	
Total	89.569	175		

Note: Dependent variable: satisfaction, * $p < .001$

Table 9. The multiple regression analysis results between destination image and satisfaction.

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Constant</i>	.202	.181		1.114	.267
Security and safety	.223	.058	.232	3.839	.000**
Environment	.162	.060	.172	2.718	.007**
Human factor	.094	.061	.107	1.536	.126
Infrastructure	.258	.084	.260	3.058	.003**
Entertainment activities	.218	.059	.233	3.714	.000**

R = .864, R² = .747, Adj R² = .739

Note: Dependent variable: satisfaction, ** *p* < .05

4.4.3. Satisfaction And Revisit Intention

Satisfaction significantly affects the intention of domestic tourists to return (Table 10 and Table 11). The analysis showed that hypothesis H3, which states that satisfaction significantly predicts the intention of domestic tourists to return to Da Lat, was accepted ($\beta = 0.776$, P-value = 0.000). Moreover, this explains 60.2% of the variation in the intention to return to Da Lat among domestic tourists. This indicates that when tourists are satisfied with Da Lat as a destination, they are likely to return.

Table 10. Summary of regression analysis for satisfaction and revisit intention.

Source	<i>SS</i>	<i>DF</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Model	62.228	1	62.228	262.730*
Error	41.212	174	.237	
Total	103.44	175		

Note: Dependent variable: revisit intention, * *p* < .001

Table 11. The regression analysis results between satisfaction and revisits intention.

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Constant</i>	.754	.212		3.549	.000*
Satisfaction	.834	.051	.776	16.209	.000*

Note: Dependent variable: revisit intention, * *p* < .001

5. Conclusion And Discussion

The study showed that destination image positively affects tourist revisit intention, consistent with previous studies (Abdullah & Lui, 2018; Ajzen, 1991; Baker & Unni, 2019; Kim, 2018; Som & Badarneh, 2011; Tosun et al., 2015). More specially, the Vietnamese domestic tourist awareness of the environment, infrastructure, and entertainment activities from Da Lat affect their revisit intention. Furthermore, the outcomes indicated that destination image positively impacts tourists' satisfaction, aligning with previous studies (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003; Thao et al., 2020; Vang et al., 2021; Vu & Vang, 2020). In particular, the perception of security and safety, environment, infrastructure, and entertainment contributed to Vietnamese tourists' satisfaction with Da Lat tourism. Finally, the result showed satisfaction positively affects tourists' intention to revisit Da La for traveling, consistence with previous studies (Chen & Tsai, 2007; Oppermann, 2000; Shi et al., 2022; Trang & Loan, 2012). Interestingly, human factors of Da Lat destination image did not show the significance to tourist satisfaction and revisit intention. It can be explained the human factor category was not well-defined or measured

accurately. The other four factors (security and safety, environment, infrastructure, and entertainment activities) were simply more important to tourists regarding overall satisfaction and revisit intention. The study participants might not perceive any significant negative experiences or interactions with the local population or service providers during their visit. The study also did not account for potential biases or cultural differences that could affect tourist perceptions of the human factor.

In the context of Da Lat tourism, a positive destination image can result in repeat tourism and increased revenue for businesses in the area. The tourism industry in Da Lat focuses on enhancing its environmental sustainability practices, improving infrastructure, and broadening the range of entertainment activities. Furthermore, tourists with a favorable impression of Da Lat, its attractions, and local services are more likely to return for future vacations and recommend the destination to others. Therefore, tourism stakeholders in Da Lat must promote a positive image of the destination through effective marketing campaigns, high-quality service, and sustainable tourism management practices. Doing so will increase the likelihood of tourists returning to the destination, leading to a sustainable tourism industry in Da Lat.

Based on the result showed that “the perception of security and safety, environment, infrastructure, and entertainment activities contributed to Vietnamese tourists’ satisfaction with Da Lat tourism,” it is clear that these factors play a critical role in ensuring that tourists have a positive experience when visiting Da Lat. The practical implication of this statement is that businesses and tourism operators in the Da Lat region should prioritize these factors to ensure that tourists feel safe, comfortable, and entertained. Da Lat might involve investing in infrastructure development, improving security measures, and offering various attractions and activities that appeal to visitors. By focusing on these critical areas, businesses can attract more tourists to Da Lat and help to bolster the local economy.

Customer satisfaction is crucial for attracting repeat visitors to the tourist destination. In order to promote sustainable tourism in Da Lat, tourism businesses, establishments, and public authorities need to prioritize customer satisfaction by providing high-quality products, services, and experiences that meet the expectations and preferences of their target audience. Thus, a sound customer relationship management strategy should be implemented to satisfy and delight customers with personalized experiences, continuous engagement, and effective problem-solving. By doing so, businesses and establishments in Da Lat will be able to increase the likelihood of repeat visits, boost the loyalty of their customers, and, ultimately, contribute to the overall growth and success of the tourism industry in the region.

In conclusion, the study implies that tourist satisfaction and perception of the Da Lat tourism destination are crucial in shaping their revisit intention. Therefore, the tourism stakeholders in Da Lat need to focus on enhancing the visitors' overall experience through a combination of measures, such as improving tourism infrastructure, quality of services, and promotion of unique tourist experiences. By taking these practical measures, Da Lat tourism destination can increase tourist revisit intentions and gain a competitive advantage in the global tourism market.

6. Limitations And Recommendation

This study on Da Lat tourism presents some limitations that should be considered. Firstly, the data to assess the hypotheses within the proposed theoretical framework were collected from tourists who visited Da Lat City. Since Da Lat is a small town in Vietnam, the results may not necessarily represent the perceptions of most Vietnamese who visit different tourist destinations throughout the country. Furthermore, the data were collected using a convenient sampling method, which might not have represented the entire tourist population in the area.

Future research can be conducted in various tourist destinations to ensure the generalizability of the findings. Most of the participants are collected students, and the results reflect their degree of perception of destination image, experience, satisfaction, and behavior that may not represent the whole population. To account for a more comprehensive analysis, future studies should involve individuals from all age groups and occupations, focusing on obtaining comparable participation percentages and comparing these groups. Finally, it is possible that the research or survey that evaluated the five factors of destination image and their impact on tourist satisfaction and revisit intention had some limitations in its methodology, sample size, or data analysis. Therefore, the findings may not generalize to all destinations or tourist populations. Future studies can consider more other factors that could affect tourist satisfaction and revisit intention, such as perceived risk, experience, or e-word of mouth.

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